

Legal Policies for Handling the Covid-19 Pandemic in the Perspective of Emergency Law and Human Rights

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Abstract

Many countries were unprepared to deal with the COVID-19 epidemic, both technically and non-technically. Many governments are still unsure whether legal tool should be utilized to cope with this non-natural calamity. Declaring an emergency may cause a government to break the law and overlook human rights for a period of time. As a result, the purpose of this research is to determine the legal politics of dealing with the COVID-19 pandemic from the standpoints of emergency law and human rights. This research employs normative legal research methods, as well as a statutory and conceptual approach. Primary legal documents (statutory rules, Session Minutes), secondary legal materials (books, journals, articles, and other scholarly works), and tertiary legal materials (legal dictionaries). According to the findings of the study, the state of emergency in Indonesia is governed by Article 12 and Article 22, paragraph 1 of the 1945 Constitution. Meanwhile, while dealing with COVID-19 in an emergency, the Indonesian government employs a legal paradigm, meaning carrying out emergency activation based on the law, in order to avoid violating Article 12. As a result, the emergency in question is not a state of emergency as defined in the study of emergency constitutional law, and it exists only *de facto*, rather than *de jure*. Finally, the emergency policy for dealing with COVID-19 must continue to respect human rights in the face of constraints.

Keywords: *Legal Policy, Covid-19, Emergency Law, Land Conditions, Human Rights.*

INTRODUCTION

Human life in all parts of the world in 2020 is experiencing a severe disaster. This disaster is included in the category of non-natural disasters that pose a severe threat to the safety of human life. This disaster is known as the COVID-19 Pandemic (Forman & Kohler, 2020). This COVID-19 pandemic is a virus that started in Wuhan, China on December 31, 2019 (Wu et al., 2020). Day by day, Covid-19 cases continue to increase. Every day can increase by about 1,000 cases. Various countries have implemented many ways to deal with this disease through various policies that lead to restrictions on the movement of people, such as closing crowds, prohibiting gatherings, closing schools and temporarily stopping office activities (Imtyaz et al., 2020).

The Coronavirus outbreak has altered people's lifestyles, interaction patterns, and behavior. The impact is enormous and far-reaching, affecting health as well as the economic, psychological, social, political, educational, cultural, and religious spheres, among others; hence, it must be addressed with proper government policies (Qiu et al., 2020). Due to the approach's inadequacy and the lack of doubt surrounding the virus's eventual demise, it will create new issues (Berardi et al., 2020). Human rights, on the other hand, are inalienable rights of citizenship bestowed by God Almighty directly onto individuals at birth and which cannot be taken away. For the honor and protection of human dignity, their existence is canceled and they must be recognized, upheld, and defended by the state, law, government, and everyone (Roziqin et al., 2021).

From a legal perspective, various countries are faced with uncertainty in choosing legal instruments that will be used to determine the various policies that will be carried out to deal with Covid-19 (Davidovitz et al., 2021). It is noted that several countries already have legal instruments that specifically regulate health crises. However, the reality is that these legal instruments are, in fact, unable to cope with the complexity of the crisis caused by the infectious virus (Lebret, 2020). Many countries do not have the relevant legal instruments to deal with the Covid-19 crisis. In addition, several countries have chosen to use their constitutional emergency provisions to respond to the Covid-19 crisis by establishing a state of emergency (Stefan, 2020)

The COVID-19 pandemic began in Indonesia on March 2, 2020. On March 2, 2020, President Joko Widodo inaugurated the first case of COVID-19 at the State Palace (Akrim, 2022). President Joko Widodo issued Presidential Decree No. 11 of 2020 on March 31, 2020, to declare a public health emergency for Corona Virus Disease 2019 (COVID-19) based on the fact that the

disease's spread has been extraordinary, with an increase in the number of cases and/or deaths, and has spread across regions and countries, and has a significant impact on public health (Fitri, 2020).

The impacts of the COVID-19 pandemic are as follows: a.) Impacts in the health sector, the easy, fast, and widespread spread of COVID-19 resulted in Health crises and Emergencies (Aeni, 2021); b.) Impact in the social sector, the cessation of socio-economic activities that absorb labour in various sectors, especially the MSME sector (Aeni, 2021); c.) Impact on the economy, economic performance declined sharply with economic growth to 2.3 (Q1) and global supply chains were immediately disrupted (Nasution et al., 2020); d.) Impacts on the financial sector, volatility and turmoil in the financial industry and a decline in investor confidence (Nasution et al., 2020); e.) Impacts on Politics and Law, the election of Regional Heads was postponed, and part of the trial process in court was hampered (Masnun et al., 2021); and f.) Impact on education, the education process is continued with an online system, but each student's ability with technology is different. Some students died when they wanted to study online because they were looking for a signal by climbing a communication tower (Siahaan, 2020).

The various impacts mentioned above show that de facto causes the Indonesian state to be in an emergency or dangerous condition (Michael, 2020). Of course, solving the problems caused by the COVID-19 pandemic requires unusual ways. To resolve an emergency or danger, an unusual instrument is needed. This instrument also overrides the rules that apply in ordinary conditions and can limit human rights (Arsil & Ayuni, 2020).

The perspective of the emergency law condition, in this case, is the various impacts that have been caused, as mentioned above, indicating that de facto causes the state of Indonesia to be in an emergency or dangerous condition. Of course, solving the problems caused by the COVID-19 pandemic requires unusual ways (Disantara, 2020). To resolve an emergency or danger, an unusual instrument is needed. This instrument also overrides the rules that apply in ordinary conditions and can limit human rights (Gultom, 2013). Public Health Emergency, a Government Regulation in Lieu of Law 1 of 2020 concerning State Financial Policy and Financial System Stability for Handling the Corona Virus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) Pandemic and/or in Facing Threats That Endanger the National Economy and/or Financial System Stability, and a Presidential Decree (Keppres) regarding Financial System Stability have all been established by the Indonesian Government to deal with the crisis (Hasibuan & Ashari, 2020). A civil emergency was also discussed by the government in the past, which is the only output of law that employs Article 12 of the 1945 Constitution and Article 22 of the 1945 Constitution in its considerations (Arsil & Ayuni, 2020).

Understanding human rights in terms of content is difficult and confusing due to changes, current realities, and the complexities of other variables (Cohen, 1993). Human rights concepts and ideals evolve over time as normative forces transform into processes of social and political change throughout the entire order of human life. 2018 (Landman) Thus, comprehending the substance of human rights requires returning to the fundamental premise of why human rights exist. Human rights exist and originate because they are basic in the sense that their application is required so that humans can develop according to their skills, aspirations, and dignity as human beings despite differences that create discrimination based on nation, race, religion, and gender (Carozza, 2008). The concepts of understanding human rights must be used as the basic foundation so that substantive understanding and comprehension of human rights become practical. These principles are based on the concepts of indivisibility and interdependence of human rights values (Buchanan, 2001).

Indonesia has been in an abnormal/dangerous/emergency state due to the COVID-19 epidemic, which has had remarkable consequences. However, the various efforts made by the government to combat the COVID-19 pandemic are not based on constitutional provisions, specifically Article 12 of the Republic of Indonesia's 1945 Constitution. The author is interested in conducting study on the Legal Politics of Handling the Covid-19 Pandemic in the Context of Emergency Law and Human Rights. In this paper, the problem is defined as how the politics of emergency law are viewed through the lens of emergency constitutional law, and how the emergency implications of Covid-19 policies in Indonesia ensure the preservation of human rights. The purpose of this research is to learn about the legal politics of COVID-19 handling policies from the perspectives of emergency law and human rights.

METHOD

Normative legal study. The normative juridical type is utilized to investigate Covid-19 Pandemic Legal Politics from the Perspective of Emergency Law and Human Rights. Due to the type of normative juridical research, the statute technique is used. This involves reviewing several laws that relate to the legal issues being treated to determine consistency and conformance (Efendi & Ibrahim, 2018). To clarify the analysis, a conceptual approach relies on legal perspectives and doctrines. This document is about experts' perspectives and doctrines on Emergency Constitutional Law and Human Rights. This study used primary, secondary, and tertiary legal materials. Primary legal resources are employed statutory-wise. The author also looks for applicable laws and regulations. This study's secondary legal materials comprised books, journals, legal articles, and

related literature. For this study's tertiary legal resources, we traced all directions to enhance and clarify primary and secondary data.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

The Concept of Emergency Constitutional Law in Indonesia

The study of emergency constitutional law is focused on a country in a state of emergency. In practice, many terminology are used in various nations to describe what defines an emergency or is connected to the definition of an emergency. They all point to nearly the same meaning: a situation of danger that unexpectedly threatens public order and necessitates the state acting in extraordinary ways in accordance with the rule of law that normally prevails under normal circumstances (Lillich, 1985).

Many names for emergency can be found in various countries' constitutions, such as in France (*etat de siege*), Germany (state of tension, state of defense), and Spain (state of alarm). In the civil law tradition, the provisions of emergency constitutional legislation are specifically stated in the constitution. America, England, and other countries, on the other hand, follow the common law legal system. This is referred to as "martial law." Meanwhile, the phrase "public emergency" is used in international human rights documents such as the European Convention on Human Rights 1950, the Inter-American Convention on Human Rights (IACHR) 1969, and the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR) 1966 (Prasetio, 2021).

As a result, it is understood that in a country in a state of emergency, constitutional law is referred to as emergency constitutional law, whereas in a country in a regular state, constitutional law is referred to as conventional constitutional law. In addition, in a country in a state of emergency, other fields of law are also of an emergency nature or in an emergency nature are only related to specific legal fields, for example, constitutional law and state administrative law. In other words, the discussion about the state in an emergency covers a broader range of material than the discussion about emergency constitutional law (Jacob, 2019). The subject of "state of emergency" must be distinguished from the issue of "emergency law", both of which have a more comprehensive content than the terms "martial law" and "constitutional law in a state of emergency".

Constitutional law in a situation of peril, according to Herman Sihombing (1996), is the creation of a series of special institutions and authorities to deal with emergencies or threats that threaten to enter the normal course of daily life, according to law and common law and usual. Meanwhile, Jimly Asshiddiqie (2008) argued about emergency constitutional law: "Therefore, in academia, especially constitutional law, it is necessary to distinguish between constitutional law that applies in ordinary or normal circumstances and constitutional law that uses in normal circumstances extraordinary or abnormal. This constitutional law is what we call emergency state law.

Under normal circumstances, the system of legal norms is enforced based on the constitution and other official legal products. In abnormal/abnormal circumstances, the legal system can function correctly. So, the regulation of emergencies has an essential meaning for actions to overcome these abnormal conditions. In abnormal circumstances (emergency), legal institutions created for normal conditions cannot work. Emergency constitutional law (*staatsnoodrecht*) is divided into two types, namely: 1) Subjective emergency constitutional law (*staatsnoodrecht subjectip*), namely the right of the state in an emergency to act by being able to deviate from the law and, if necessary it can also deviate from the constitution. Subjective emergency constitutional law is grounded in human rights law or human rights. The purpose of the Subjective emergency constitutional law is to provide immediate protection for the human rights of individuals whose safety is imperiled by an imminent threat. Subjective emergency constitutional law is an unwritten law that is recognized internationally; 2) Objective constitutional law (*staatsnoodrecht objetip*), is the law that applies during a state of emergency. Urgent constitutional statute the primary purpose is codified law. Formalized teachings on the rule of law contributed to the emergence of an objective emergency constitutional law. Where in the formal teachings of the rule of law it is stated that the characteristics of the rule of law are: The existence of recognition and protection of human rights; a division of power (*trias politica*); the government must be based on written laws (the principle of legality); and the existence of an administrative court (Nuh, 2011).

Law Number 23 Prp of 1959, as amended by Law Number 52 of 1960 concerning Dangerous Conditions, stipulates three levels of emergency: a state of war emergency, martial law, and civil emergency. In the law, it can be understood that the three types of emergencies mentioned above require a presidential decree as the source and basis for the legitimacy of the emergency. Jimly Asshiddiqie (2008) said that the implementation of the emergency must be preceded by an official statement or proclamation that makes it legal to take actions that violate ordinary law. Suppose the proclamation or declaration of a

state of emergency is not carried out while the steps taken violate common law. Such an emergency is called a "de facto emergency", which must be avoided in every state of law. Making a declaration or proclamation means that there is a legal action in the form of a legally binding decision. With this proclamation, the legal status of a state of emergency becomes valid and can be referred to as an "emergency de jure".

In the 1945 Constitution of the Republic of Indonesia, provisions regarding an emergency are regulated in two articles, namely Article 12 and Article 22 paragraph (1). Where the first two articles use the term "state of danger," which is nothing but the same as an emergency (state of emergency), while the second term uses the term "matter of compelling urgency". In practice, both can carry the same practical meaning. Therefore, a state of danger is sometimes considered the same as an event of dangerous urgency, or conversely, a hazardous event is the same as an emergency. Thus, the condition of urgency that compels it is wider than the state of danger. Therefore, the two terms "a state of danger" and "a matter of compelling urgency" can be distinguished. With this distinction, it is natural that the stipulation of government regulation as a substitute for a law based on Article 22 paragraph (1) of the 1945 Constitution does not have to be preceded by a declaration of a state of emergency. Meanwhile, the implementation of Article 12 of the 1945 Constitution requires that an official declaration or proclamation be made in the context of implementing the dangerous situation.

As Jimly Asshiddiqie (2008) underlined, Article 22 of the 1945 Constitution refers to conditions and problems of urgency, yet Article 12 of the 1945 Constitution refers to a "state of danger." As defined in Article 22 of the 1945 Constitution, a situation or matter of coercive urgency falls under the definition of "condition of danger" as defined in Article 12. Article 12 of the 1945 Constitution, on the other hand, does not always imply a condition of danger based on Article 22 of the 1945 Constitution. As stated in Article 22 of the 1945 Constitution, the term "state of danger" has a much broader meaning than Article 12. It is perfectly legal for Presidents to impose government regulations rather than laws in the event of an imminent threat. Dangerous items are also dangerous conditions, and vice versa. The country is in peril because of the dangers it faces, and vice versa. Of course, danger is usually accompanied by "coercive urgency," but danger does not always accompany problems of "compelling urgency." But the President's declaration of a Perppu does not always signify that there is an imminent threat.

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Legal Politics of Handling COVID-19 According to the Perspective of Emergency Law

The legal scheme approach was described by Tom Ginsburg and Mila Versteeg (2014) as the choice of nations around the world to implement crises in the face of the Covid-19 epidemic. For governments around the world, they offer three methods of emergency response. For starters, countries that desire to implement emergency activation in accordance with their constitutions might declare a state of emergency. In the second case, countries that opt to deploy legal instruments at the statutory level, such as those relating to public health and national disasters, already have legislation in place (legislative model). The third step is the enactment of new emergency laws. The Covid-19 outbreak has prompted these countries to enact new legislation (Ginsburg & Versteeg, 2021).

Each of these emergency possibilities has repercussions for democracy and freedom, according to the analysis offered. The constitutional emergency option (first choice) is analogous to the terms of the State of Danger in Article 12 of the 1945 Constitution. Giving emergency authorities broad authority allows them to violate different legal and human rights norms with little oversight. The same problem exists in other nations as it does in Indonesia, namely, the concept of an emergency is more centered on an emergency owing to security disruptions. There are very few countries where the constitution expressly states that disasters, particularly those caused by disease transmission, are grounds for declaring a state of emergency. As a result, the usage of this sort of emergency is less focused and may jeopardize freedom and democracy (Thomson & Ip, 2020).

In Indonesia, policymakers are dealing with the Covid-19 pandemic, therefore the choice of legislative model, meaning carrying out emergency activation based on the law, is dominating. This decision was marked by the issuance of Presidential Decree Number 11 of 2020 concerning the Determination of the Corona Virus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) Public Health Emergency, which was followed by the issuance of Presidential Decree Number 12 of 2020 concerning the Determination of Non-Natural Disasters for the Spread of Corona Virus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) as National Disasters, which is the ac (Catfish, 2021).

The activation of these two laws seeks to explicitly address public health and non-natural disaster emergencies, in accordance with what Ginsburg and Versteeg refer to as the use of existing legislation dealing with public health or national disasters, or what Ferejohn & Pasquino refer to as the legislative model. The choice of this legal scheme does not cause the emergency authority to become very large and fast in executing policies. Still, the law-based emergency approach makes the emergency policy perspective more specific to public health and disasters because the law on public health and disaster is used. Therefore, the powers of the emergency authorities are focused and very limited, and all provisions in the constitution can still work to protect the rights of citizens (Rissy, 2020).

With this policy choice, it should not be found that the fundamental rights of citizens will be restricted. Even if residents feel that their rights have been violated, they can still apply for their fulfilment through legal or political channels. In its various provisions, there are indeed restrictions on the expression of citizens in carrying out their activities, but they are not directly related to the material freedom of expression. The limits imposed are more on technical meetings and the movement of citizens to prevent transmission. The limitation of the mechanism for meeting residents in direct meeting forums does not mean that there is a ban on discussion materials, nor does the restriction of carrying out activities in places of worship mean that there are restrictions on online studies and study materials.

The choice to avoid emergency declarations based on the constitution in various countries has similar reasons to Indonesia. The powers of emergency rulers will be enormous, and more citizens' freedom can deviate with limited political and legal control. Therefore, the potential for deviation by the emergency authorities is wide open. Declarations of constitutional-based emergencies in democratic countries tend to be reserved as "safety valves" if activation of statutory emergencies alone is not sufficient to deal with crises.

In order to deal with Covid-19, Indonesia has chosen to enact new emergency legislation. For dealing with the 2019 Covid-19 pandemic as well as threats to the national economy and financial system stability, Perppu No. 1 of 2020 will be issued, as well as Perppu No. 2 concerning the third amendment to Law No. 1 of 2015 concerning Stipulation of Government Regulations, instead of Law No. 1 of 2014 concerning the Elections for Governors, Regent, and Mayor. These two law-level regulations were indeed issued during a pandemic and are related to the pandemic, and also the extraordinary powers are given to them by their makers. Indeed, this Perppu allows the government to form significant state finances with limited control, much different from that found in standard times (Ginsburg & Versteeg, 2021).

Suitability of Emergency Handling COVID-19 in the Perspective of Human Rights

The term human rights itself comes from the terms *droits l'home* (French), *menselijke recent* (Dutch), *fitrah* (Arabic) and human rights (English). The term human rights originally came from 'right of human', which replaced the term 'natural right', which was later changed by Eleanor Roosevelt with the term 'human right', which has a more neutral and universal connotation (Salim, 2021). According to Jan Materson from the UN Human Rights Commission, and Baharudin Lopa (1996), human rights are inherent in every human being. Humans can't live as humans. Furthermore, according to Eisler (1987), human rights are rights given directly by God as natural rights.

As a result, according to Jan Materson, human rights might be broadly described as those rights ingrained in our nature, without which we are unable to function properly as human beings. Human rights are typically seen as inalienable liberties that no one can take away, even if they are violated by a legitimate authority. This is due to the inherent character of human rights. When it comes to protecting human rights, those who violate them must be punished severely by the state or government. The government is responsible for ensuring that human rights are protected, promoted, enforced, and fulfilled; the 1945 Constitution explicitly specifies this (Lopa, 1996).

The global Covid-19 pandemic, according to Amnesty International Indonesia, impacted at least four human rights (Agustina et al., 2021), namely:

1. Right to Health

As stated in Article 4 of Law 36 of 2009 on Health (Health Law) and Article 9 (3) of Law no. 39 of 1999 concerning Human Rights, "the State is obliged to improve environmental and industrial health, the prevention, treatment and control of all infectious, endemic and other occupational diseases, and the creation of conditions to guarantee all medical care and attention." Disaster Management for vulnerable groups, such as the elderly, infants, toddlers, children, pregnant or breastfeeding women and people with disabilities are covered by Article 55 of Law No. 24 of 2007 on Disaster Management for Vulnerable Groups.

2. Right to Information

Another human right that has been impacted by the Covid-19 outbreak is the right to information. Article 154 (1) of the health law states that if a disorder has the potential to spread, the government must quickly identify and publish the symptoms and methods of transmission. Certain areas of the body are more susceptible to infection. Health care providers need to be aware of this information to respond successfully to epidemics. Covid-19 delays and a lack of openness could harm public health by preventing health care practitioners and the general public from implementing the most effective preventative actions feasible.

3. Right to Privacy

Additionally, the Covid-19 epidemic poses a threat to the individual's right to privacy. First two patients who tested positive for corona felt pressured by the tremendous media coverage that governmental officials imparted, according to many media sources. In addition, the news' influence extends to others in one's immediate social circle, such as family members, friends, and even one's neighbors. Since the passage of Law No. 14 in 2008, individuals' rights to privacy and disclosure of personal information have been safeguarded. If a person's history, the health of their family, or their own physical and mental well-being warrants an exception, it can be given. It is therefore illegal to reveal the identities of corona victims.

4. Right to Work

From home industry workers to MSMEs (micro, small and medium enterprises), workers in the formal and informal sectors are emancipated by the adoption of Large-Scale Social Restrictions (PSBB) with social distance regulations and working from home. Afraid of losing their jobs due to wage cuts, denial of paid time off, or termination of employment (PHK).

Government Regulation No. 1 of 2020 concerning State Financial Policy and Financial System Stability for Handling the Covid-19 Pandemic and in Facing Threats That Endanger the National Economy, and Financial System Stability, was stipulated on March 31. Accordingly, Juridical handling of the Covid-19 pandemic is motivated by its influence on delaying national economic growth, reducing state income, and increasing state spending and financing, among other things. These factors necessitate a federal response that focuses on health and social safety nets in addition to economic recovery for the corporate world as a whole. There are also serious legal issues with PERPPU Number 1 of 2020, such as the potential for moral hazard, fraud and corruption when officials cannot be sued in a civil, criminal or state administrative manner for every action or decision done by them.

If you look at the appeals and laws, they don't seem to fit the definition of human rights. PPKM (Enforcement of Restrictions on Community Activities) is a good policy in principle for breaking the chain of Covid-19 spread, but the principle of human rights is not fulfilled because a policy to provide sources of life and livelihood for communities is not followed. This discrepancy can be seen from the existing concrete facts.

Reflecting on the declaration that restrictions on human rights can be carried out in health emergencies and non-natural disaster emergencies selected by Indonesia, it has been mentioned above that the two emergency statuses are declared apart from the state of emergency based on the constitution. Although formally it is said to be an emergency, the two states of emergency are only de facto. It is said so because the legal product, which is the basis for its implementation, does not involve the provisions of Article 12 of the 1945 Constitution as an article that activates the enactment of a constitutional emergency. Therefore, the reductions made while the two emergency statuses are in effect must not touch the fundamental rights of a substantial nature—moreover, the reduction for non-derogable rights groups as stated in Article 28 of the 1945 Constitution.

In Indonesia, Law No. 6 of 2018 regulates the supply of compensation or benefits in adopting large-scale social restriction policies by requiring the government to protect public health from sickness and potential public health risk factors. Induce a health emergency by imposing a community-wide quarantine. (Article 4). During the regional quarantine period, the central government is responsible for providing the inhabitants of the quarantine area with food and other essentials. (Article 55 paragraph (1)). Then, Article 8 states that everyone is entitled to vital health services during the quarantine time, in addition to

medical care, food, and other daily necessities. The phrase "other daily essentials" refers to various clothing and toiletries, as well as washing and defecating. Additionally, everyone has the right to receive the same treatment when a health quarantine is implemented.

CONCLUSION

The Covid-19 disease is both natural and dangerous in that it spreads more easily than the preceding disease. This condition has a significant impact on the community's economics, politics, law, society, and culture. The issuance of Presidential Decree Number 11 of 2020 concerning the Determination of the Corona Virus Disease 2019 (Covid-19) Public Health Emergency, which was followed by the activation of Law Number 6 of 2018 concerning Health Quarantine, which was then followed by the issuance of a Decree President Number 12 of 2020 concerning the Determination of Non-Natural Disasters for the Spread of Corona Virus Disease. In its execution, the decision of the emergency situation for handling COVID-19 does not meet Article 12 of the 1945 Constitution, which allows the state to diverge from the constitution and suspend the state's obligations in fulfilling human rights for a specified length of time. In dealing with the COVID-19 emergency, the Indonesian government prioritizes the legislative model established by Law 24 of 2007 and Health Emergencies established by Law 6 of 2018. This is done to ensure that the implementation of COVID-19's emergency handling does not overlook the fulfillment of essential human rights, which are human rights. Human rights of all people, such as the right to health, the right to information, privacy, and the right to work, cannot be realized if Article 12 of the 1945 Constitution is followed.

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